

Improving mortar properties with waste wind turbine blade fibers and superplasticizer

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ABSTRACT

The growing waste from decommissioned wind turbine blades (WTB) sets environmental challenges, with landfilling as the common disposal method. This study aims to explore the potential of recycling WTB fiber (WTBF) into cement mortar as a reinforcement material, specifically investigating its effects on workability, strength, hydration process, microstructure, and shrinkage. 0.5, 1, and 2 vol% of WTBF were incorporated into mortars with and without superplasticizer (SP), and tests were conducted on flow, strength, and hydration kinetics. The results show that adding WTBF with SP incorporation significantly improves the flowability (11–14.58 cm, 11.8–15.93 cm, and 12.6–17.33 cm, respectively) and compressive strength (up to 100 % increase) of the mortar. Furthermore, SP enhanced WTBF-matrix bonding, reduced porosity, and strengthened the composites. These findings enable the usage of WTBF-reinforced mortars in practical applications, e.g. 3D printed mortar, which requires a typical flowability ranging from 13 to 18 cm.

1. Introduction

The growing production of wind turbines (WT), driven by the positive environmental impact and increasing global energy demand of the industrial sector, has led to a substantial accumulation of wind turbine blade (WTB) waste [1–3]. Although approximately 85–90 % of decommissioned wind turbine components—including towers, foundations, generators, and gearboxes—are recycled, the composite nature of the blades makes their separation and reprocessing challenging and time-consuming [4]. This complexity often leads to landfilling as the preferred, cost-effective disposal method, despite high taxation and associated environmental harm [5]. A promising strategy to address this challenge involves incorporating WTB waste into cement-based materials [6–8]. Given that the recycling process of WTB typically yields fiber-like products after mechanical shredding, these fibers can be utilized as fiber reinforcement [6,9,10]. Nevertheless, the influence of these fibers on the mechanical and durability properties of cementitious products remains largely unknown, demanding further investigation.

Previously, an increasing amount of research explored the incorporation of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) into the mix design of construction materials to utilize FRP while preserving or even improving the engineering properties of the materials [11]. Specifically, Tao et al. [12] reported that FPR recycles reduced drying shrinkage and enhanced

mortar strength. Liu et al. [13] also stated that high shrinkage in infra-lightweight concrete were reduced by FPR reinforcement. The different types and contents of fibers also influenced the shrinkage behavior, as reported by Zhang et al. [14]. Interestingly, although the use of superplasticizers correlates with an increase in the drying shrinkage of the cementitious matrix [15], the different fiber sizes impact the shrinkage [16]. Generally, the longer fiber can result in better adherence between fibers and matrix, positively mitigating drying shrinkage [16]. It is worth noting that WTB waste is a kind of FRP consisting of two major compounds: epoxy resin and glass fiber [17,18]. Xu et al. [1] found that incorporating WTB fiber (WTBF) into a concrete mix enhanced flexural strength by 37.85 % at a 2.5 % reinforcement level. This improvement was attributed to the increased residual strength in the post-peak deflection softening phase of the flexural load-deflection curve. Ortega-López et al. [19] analyzed the potential of raw-crushed WTB (RCWTB) as reinforcement to increase concrete ductility and to strengthen load-bearing capacity using different tests to analyze the stress-strain performance, the deflection behavior under bending, and the deformational behavior under indirect-tensile stresses. Fu et al. [20] reinforced concrete with varying amounts of wind turbine blade fibers (WTBF), observing that higher WTBF volumes generally resulted in increased flexural strength. Pławecka et al. [21] incorporated WTBF as reinforcement in geopolymer and found that adding 5–15 %

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WTBF by weight resulted in compressive and flexural strengths comparable to control samples. Those previous studies revealed that the mechanical recycling of WTBF waste yields fiber-like WTBF waste with different sizes that has the potential to be utilized as fiber reinforcement in cement-based materials. Therefore, the waste WTBF may be used to enhance the durability of cement-based materials, specifically mitigating the drying shrinkage of the matrix.

The shrinkage of cement-based materials is influenced by various factors, such as the water-to-cement ratio (W/C) [22,23] and fiber reinforcement. These factors also affect the workability of the mixture in its fresh state, as well as its strength. Song et al. [24] reported that fiber-reinforced mortars have relatively poor flowability compared to reference mortars without fibers. The water absorption of fiber influences the flowability of the fresh mixing cement composites. Other researchers [24] reported that alkyl ketene dimer (AKD)-modified fibers exhibited hydrophobic properties, which increased the workability. Sun et al. [25] also stated that when more polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fiber was added the rotor had to overcome a large cohesive force of the mixture to turn up, and the workability of the mixture decreased. Consequently, the poor flowability of high-PVA fiber-containing samples resulted in poor compressive strength compared to reference samples. Both studies bring up a debt on the correlation between strength and fiber type, which leaves questions about how WTBF influences workability and strength.

The workability of the fresh state of the mixture can be affected by the incorporation of superplasticizers (SP). Ren et al. [26] investigated the effects of SP on workability. Results showed that SP significantly improved the workability of the cementitious mixture. Similarly, Basser et al. [27] reported that increasing the percentage of fiber replacement caused a decrease in the workability of mixtures, while SP compensated for the reduction of the workability due to fiber additions. Although the SP addition leads to better workability of the fiber-reinforced cement-based matrix, the hydration process can be affected. A higher dosage of SP always delays the hydration process, and the postponing effect continuously increases even after the SP addition exceeds the saturation dosages [28]. Mezhev et al. [29] also reported the retardation mechanism of cement hydration by SP. The early degree of hydration (less than 12 hours) was delayed, but the degree of hydration was almost the same between the reference samples and SP-involved samples after 72 hours [29]. Those investigations revealed the retardation effect of SP on the hydration kinetics. Furthermore, the extended hydration time of SP affects the evolution of the microstructure. Gong et al. [30] stated that the addition of SP extended the induction time of the hydration process, thus mitigating the formation of microscopic defects. Therefore, SP reduced the porosity of the cement-based matrix, leading to a denser microstructure. Previous studies have shown the effect of SP on fiber-reinforced cement-based matrix while incorporating WTBF into cement mortar is a new and innovative technique worldwide, and it is crucial to provide information on the practical application of WTBF in mortar (with and without SP). Simultaneously, the basic information of WTBF-reinforced mortar is unknown in terms of the hydration process and microstructure evolution. This hinders the application process of WTBF, which seriously restricts the application of WTBF in actual practice. An initial study of the effect of WTBF on the cement-based matrix should be conducted.

This study aimed to investigate recycling WTBF into mortar as fiber reinforcement with and without SP. The flow of the WTBF-reinforced mortar (with and without SP) was studied, and the strength of the mortars was also determined. The hydration kinetic and microstructure of WTBF-reinforced paste were investigated. Furthermore, the shrinkage of WTBF-reinforced mortar was studied as well. The findings of this study demonstrate that SP effectively mitigates the negative effects of WTBF incorporation, significantly enhancing workability without compromising mechanical performance. This optimized balance between fresh and hardened properties provides solid evidence for tailoring mix designs to end users for specific applications, such as 3D printing or self-compacting concrete (SCC), making it a promising

approach for sustainable construction materials.

2. Experiments

2.1. Materials and sample preparations

WTBF sourcing from Spain (PreZero) was employed in this experiment. The received WTBF was mechanically shredded from the retired WTBF into random sizes, all smaller than 80 mm (shown in Fig. 1(a)). CEM I 52.5 R sourcing from Denmark (Aalborg Portland) was used as a binder for a rapid hydration reaction. Superplasticizer (SP) was DYNAMON XTEND 391 from MAPEI company in Denmark. The detailed characterization of cement and WTBF is presented in Section 3.1. The mix design of the control sample and WTBF-reinforced samples are listed in Table 1. The sand usage in mortar was class E originating from Denmark locally (ranging from 1 to 4 mm).

2.2. Testing methods

XRF

The WTBF material was finely ground for homogeneity. 1 g of ground WTBF was mixed with 10 g of flux (99.5 % $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 0.5 % LiI) and heated in a platinum or platinum-gold crucible at 950–1100°C for 25 min in a muffle furnace. The fusion process fully dissolved the sample, forming a molten mixture, which was poured into a preheated mold to solidify into a fused glass bead. Cement powder followed the same procedure. The fused beads were analyzed using an XRF spectrometer (LeNeo Fluxer).

Sieving test

The sieving of the WTBF was performed by passing the sieves 63 μm , 125 μm , 250 μm , 500 μm , 1 mm, 2 mm, 4 mm, and 8 mm with nine different groups (<63 μm , 63–125 μm , 125–250 μm , 250–500 μm , 500 μm –1 mm, 1–2 mm, 2–4 mm, 4–8 mm, and >8 mm). The sieving process was performed in the sieving machine for 5 mins.

XRD

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of ground WTBF and cement powder was conducted using an X Pert PRO instrument, which emitted $\text{Co-K}\alpha$ radiation (40 kV, 30 mA). The ground WTBF and cement powder were subjected to measurements with a step size of 0.05° and a counting time of 1 s/step. The scanning range for 2θ was set between 10 and 70°.

Strength

The mortar mixing procedure followed EN 196–1 [31]. Then the mortar was then cast into 40 × 40 × 160 mm³ molds for curing. After 28 days of curing (20°C, 95 % RH), flexural strength was tested at 50 N/s until fracture, followed by compressive strength on the remaining parts at 2400 N/s. Each mix strength was averaged from three samples. And the testing was also followed EN 196–1 [31].

Flow table test

Workability was assessed using the flow table test (BS EN 12350–5 [32]). The flow table was placed on a stable surface, cleaned, and dampened. A cone was centered, filled in two layers, and tamped 10 times per layer. Excess mortar was leveled off, and after 10–30 s, the cone was lifted in 1–3 s. Within 10 s, the table was stabilized, then dropped 15 times in 1–3 s cycles. The maximum spread was measured in two perpendicular directions.

SEM

After the compressive strength tests of samples at 28 days, the fragments of the Ref and W2 mortar samples were collected. The microstructure of the polished samples was examined by Quanta FEI FEG – 250 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument.

Isothermal calorimeter

According to the mixture proportion in Table 1, the heat evolution of the pastes (with WTBF) was characterized with an isothermal calorimeter (I-Cal Flex). In particular, the paste mix design was similar to the mortar mix design but without sand. All the pastes were injected into the sample container after a 5-minute mixing period. Heat flow and

Fig. 1. (a) Raw WTBF before sieving; (b) Particle size distribution of WTBF after sieving test.

Table 1
Mortar samples (unit: g).

Sample ID	Cement	Sand	WTBF	Water	SP	Mark
Ref	100	300	-	50	-	Control sample
W0.5	100	300	2.06	50	-	0.5 vol% of WTBF in mortar
W1	100	300	4.12	50	-	1 vol% of WTBF in mortar
W2	100	300	8.24	50	-	2 vol% of WTBF in mortar
Ref-P	100	300	-	50	1	The control sample with 1 wt% SP
W0.5-P	100	300	2.06	50	1	0.5 vol% of WTBF + 1 wt% SP in mortar
W1-P	100	300	4.12	50	1	1 vol% of WTBF + 1 wt% SP in mortar
W2-P	100	300	8.24	50	1	2 vol% of WTBF + 1 wt% SP in mortar
Ref-S	100	200	-	50	-	Control sample for shrinkage testing
W0.063-2	100	200	4.12	50	-	1 vol% of 0.063–2 mm WTBF for shrinkage testing
W2-8	100	200	4.12	50	-	1 vol% of 2–8 mm WTBF for shrinkage testing
W8+	100	200	4.12	50	-	1 vol% of > 8 mm WTBF for shrinkage testing

hydration heat data are continuously recorded for 7 days (168 h). Cumulative heat release and hydration exothermal rate were obtained and analyzed to study the hydration of the WTBF-reinforced cement matrix. It should be noted that the values measured during the initial 45 minutes might slightly deviate as it takes time to stabilize the inner measurement environment [33]. Therefore, the initial 45 minutes were excluded from the final data.

Shrinkage

The free drying shrinkage test followed ASTM C157 standard [34] on mortar level. For each test parameter, three prismatic specimens measuring 285 × 25 × 25 mm were prepared. The average free drying shrinkage was calculated from 7 days up to 28 days.

Table 2
Raw materials compositions (unit: wt%).

Group	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Others	LOI*
Ground WTBF	1.95	1.69	12.39	56.45	/	0.57	25.02	0.70	0.40	0.83	55.97
Cement I	1.02	0.88	3.41	18.69	3.31	/	68.23	/	3.25	1.21	2.45

LOI*=Loss on ignition at 950°C

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of raw materials

Table 2 presents the raw material compositions of ground wind turbine blade fiber (WTBF) and Cement I 52.5 R. The primary components of ground WTBF included a high proportion of SiO₂ at 56.45 wt%, CaO at 25.02 wt%, and Al₂O₃ at 12.39 wt%. These three constituents accounted for the majority of the composition, indicating that the WTBF is rich in silicates and aluminates, typical of fiber-reinforced materials used in composite structures. The loss on ignition (LOI) of WTBF was notably high at 55.97 wt%, which suggests the presence of high amounts of organic matter (mainly from epoxy resins) that are burned off during heating at 950°C. The LOI was calculated by testing after XRF remaining residual.

The raw material and mass fraction of WTBF after the sieving process are presented in Fig. 1. The red dashed line shows the incremental WTBF waste (shown in Fig. 1(b)). The incremental waste percentage remains relatively low and stable for particle sizes below 1000 μm. However, a noticeable increase occurs beyond this threshold, with a sharp peak at larger particle sizes, indicating a significant proportion of the WTBF is found in these coarser fractions. The solid black line represents the cumulative WTBF waste, which shows a progressive accumulation of WTBF waste as the particle size increases. The cumulative WTBF remains steady up to approximately 100 μm but then starts to rise more rapidly. A sharp incline occurs after 1000 μm, reflecting the substantial contribution of larger particles to the total WTBF waste. This trend reaches its maximum as the cumulative WTBF approaches 100 %, confirming that the majority of the WTBF is concentrated in larger particle sizes.

XRD of WTBF (Fig. 2(a)) shows a small amount of calcite, which may be the filler material in the blade [35]. Rutile (TiO₂), a polymorph of titanium dioxide, is also represented. TiO₂ is often used as a pigment in the manufacturing of wind turbine blades [36]. The hump in the WTBF diffractogram shows that the material is highly amorphous and is likely an amorphous silicon compound. XRD of cement is also shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Fig. 2. XRD of raw materials (a) Ground WTBF; (b) Cement.

3.2. Properties of the composites

3.2.1. Flowability

Fig. 3 illustrates the mean diameter of mortar flow for different mortar samples incorporating WTBF, with and without the addition of SP. The reference sample (Ref) exhibited a mean flow diameter of 13.38 cm in the absence of SP, which significantly increased to 18 cm (an increase of 34.5 %) upon SP addition. This trend was consistent across all WTBF-reinforced samples. Specifically, the W0.5 sample showed an increase in flow diameter from 12.6 cm to 17.33 cm (an increase of 37.5 %), the W1 sample from 11.8 cm to 15.93 cm (an increase of 35 %), and the W2 sample from 11 cm to 14.58 cm (an increase of 32.5 %) when SP was added.

These results indicate that the addition of SP substantially enhances the workability of mortar, as reflected by the increased flow diameters. The improved workability is likely due to the reduction in internal friction between particles, which allows for better dispersion and ease of flow. The impact of SP is particularly noticeable in the WTBF-containing samples, where the fibrous nature of the waste tends to reduce workability in the absence of SP. These findings agree with previous studies, showing that higher fiber content reduces workability [37]. This effect may be attributed to the shape and surface texture of WTBF particles, which generate internal friction within the mortar mixture, necessitating additional cement paste to mitigate this friction. Furthermore, the

Fig. 3. Flow of WTBF reinforced mortar with and without SP.

hydrophilic nature of the fibers contributes to water absorption [38], resulting in reduced water availability within the mixture particles as the percentage of WTBF increases. In summary, the results demonstrate the efficacy of SPs in enhancing the workability of WTBF-reinforced mortar mixtures. This meets the flowability requirements for 3D-printed fresh mixtures, which typically range from 130 to 180 mm, making WTBF-reinforced mortar a potential candidate for such applications [39].

3.2.2. Strength

Fig. 4 shows the compressive strength and flexural strength of WTBF-reinforced mortars with and without SPs at 28 days, respectively. Generally, the SP improves the strength of the mortars, leading to a higher performance.

The reference sample (Ref) showed a compressive strength of 46.9 MPa without SP, which increased to 65.2 MPa with SP, resulting in a 39 % increase. For the W0.5 sample, the compressive strength increased from 41.3 MPa to 65.1 MPa, marking a 58 % increase. The W1 sample exhibited a notable improvement, with its compressive strength rising from 37.9 MPa to 63.5 MPa, reflecting a 68 % increase. The most substantial enhancement was observed in the W2 sample, which saw its compressive strength jump from 28.2 MPa to 56.6 MPa, representing a remarkable 101 % increase due to SP. Fig. 4(a) provides a concise comparison of the Compressive strengths at 28 days for different samples, showing the impact of both including and excluding SP and their corresponding strength gains. These results emphasize the significant enhancement in compressive strength achieved by incorporating SP.

Fig. 4(b) illustrates the results of flexural strength, comparing samples with and without SP at 28 days. The flexural strengths increased by approximately 24 % for Ref (from 6.7 to 8.3), 19 % for W0.5 (from 6.7 to 8), 30 % for W1 (from 6.9 to 9), and 31 % for W2 (from 5.9 to 7.7) when SP was added. Fig. 4(b) provides a concise comparison of the flexural strengths at 28 days for different samples, showing the impact of both including and excluding SP and their corresponding strength gains. The results clearly demonstrate that samples incorporating SP consistently exhibited higher flexural strengths compared to those without, showing strength gains ranging from 19 % to 31 %. The incorporation of WTBF generally increases flexural strength but decreases compressive strength, while SP significantly enhances mechanical performance.

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the flow of mortar and compressive strength at 28 days of curing. A positive correlation between flow diameter and compressive strength was observed for both the samples with and without SP. For the samples with and without SP, the relationship followed a linear trend, indicating that as the flow diameter increases, the compressive strength also tends to increase.

The results suggest that the addition of SP not only enhances the workability of mortar but also has a positive influence on compressive

Fig. 4. Mortars with and without SP at 28 days (a) Compressive strength; (b) Flexural strength.

Fig. 5. Correlations between compressive strength and flow of mortars.

strength, especially in mixtures containing WTBF. The increase in flow diameter with SP addition indicates improved workability, which likely enhances compaction and hydration during curing, leading to higher

compressive strength. However, achieving optimal mechanical performance requires balancing WTBF content with both workability and compressive strength, as excessive WTBF may reduce workability and hinder proper consolidation. While SPs can effectively mitigate the reduced workability caused by fibrous waste materials, careful control of mix proportions is necessary to ensure strength development by proper flowability.

3.2.3. Isothermal calorimeter

Fig. 6 illustrated the normalized heat flow and cumulative heat release for 4 samples containing 0 vol% (Ref), 0.5 vol% (W0.5), 1 vol% (W1), and 2 vol% (W2) of WTBF over 168 hours.

Fig. 6(a), presents the normalized heat flow against time on a logarithmic scale, highlighting five distinct periods: Initial, Dormant, Acceleration, Deceleration, and Diffusion/Stable [40]. All samples initially exhibited a high heat flow, which rapidly declined during the Initial Period and remained low during the Dormant Period. A significant increase in heat flow occurred during the Acceleration Period, peaking at around 12 hours for all samples, with varying peak values across different WTBF contents. This was followed by a decline in the Deceleration Period and stabilization in the Diffusion/Stable Period. Although the peak values differ, these results suggest that WTBF content influences the hydration process.

Fig. 6(b) shows the normalized cumulative heat at 168 hours. It was observed that the cumulative heat of W1 at 160 hours is higher than Ref, W0.5, and W2, respectively. The extra heat release of W1 might be due

Fig. 6. Calorimeter data of WTBF reinforced mortar (a) Normalized heat flow; (b) Normalized total heat release.

to the more glass from WTBF exposure to the alkali environment of the pore solution in cement. This is also in line with the highest strength of W1 in Section 3.2.2.

Fig. 7 shows the heat evolution over 160 hours for four samples with SP: Ref, W0.5, W1, and W2. The hydration process can be seen in Fig. 7 (a), as it is noticeable all the peaks of the samples are very similar in time, it can be assumed that the length of each stage is almost the same for every sample. It can be seen from Fig. 7(a) that the peak of heat of hydration of W0.5, W1, and W2 follow a descending trend at 19.5 hours compared to the Ref sample, this trend shows an inverse proportionality to WTBF content, the higher the WTBF the lower heat of hydration is.

Fig. 7(b) displays the total heat released at 160 hours. It is evident that the cumulative heat of W0.5, W1, and W2 follow the same trend as the heat of hydration with respect to the control (Ref) sample. The SP promotes a homogeneous distribution of the WTBF in the cement paste, while the increased WTBF content introduces a retarder effect, leading to reduced heat release during the cement hydration process. Therefore, the higher WTBF content results in lower heat release as a result of retarder in the cement paste.

Fig. 8 compares the heat evolution over 160 hours, excluding the first hour, for four samples: Ref, W0.5, W1, and W2, both with and without SP. The hydration process is displayed in Fig. 8(a). It is observed that the dormant period for the samples with SP was longer than for the samples without SP. Consequently, the hydration process is delayed by about 8 hours. This is in line with the previous study [28]. The SP brings the retarding effect on the hydration process. Additionally, the peaks of the heat of hydration for all samples with SP are lower than those without SP.

Fig. 8(b) also compares the total heat released starting at 50–160 hours. It is noted that the cumulative heat of all samples with SP is lower than those without SP, following the same trend as the heat of hydration. The percentage change in total heat release between samples with and without SP highlights the largest decrease of 16 % observed for W1.

Fig. 9 presents the compressive strength at 28 days versus total heat release for samples with and without SP, including Ref, W0.5, W1, and W2 samples. The Ref sample exhibits the highest compressive strength both with and without SP, increasing from 46.89 MPa to 65.23 MPa. The W0.5 sample with SP shows compressive strength nearly identical to the Ref sample with SP, increasing from 65.2 MPa to 65.1 MPa, marking a 58 % increase. W1 also demonstrates substantial improvement, increasing from 37.86 MPa without SP to 63.5 MPa with SP, a 68 % increase. The W2 sample has the lowest compressive strength without SP at 28.15 MPa but showed significant improvement with SP, reaching 56.58 MPa, a 100 % increase.

Additionally, adding SP reduces the total heat release for all samples,

with Ref decreasing from approximately 260 J/g to 242 J/g, W0.5 from 258 J/g to 232 J/g, W1 from 264 J/g to 222 J/g, and W2 from 253 J/g to 221 J/g. Incorporating SP significantly enhances the compressive strength of fiber-reinforced mortars but reduces the total heat release across the samples. The W0.5 sample with SP is the best performer overall, as it closely matches the compressive strength of the Ref sample while maintaining a lower total heat release. This suggests that W0.5 with SP offers a balanced improvement in both strength and hydration efficiency, making it an optimal choice for practical applications where both high strength and efficient curing are desired.

3.2.4. SEM

Fig. 10 illustrates the microstructure of Ref samples with and without SP at 500x and 1000x magnifications. For the Ref sample with SP, Fig. 10 (a) (left) at 500x exhibits loose ITZ regions around solid aggregates influenced by the SP. However, visible cracks exist, suggesting ongoing concerns about structural integrity. Fig. 10 (a) (right) at 1000x reveals lower-density ITZs regions around aggregates despite potential improvements in workability. In the scenario of Ref sample without SP, Fig. 10 (b) (left) at 500x shows loose Interfacial Transition Zones (ITZs) around solid aggregates, with the cement matrix as the main bonding component, indicating potential vulnerabilities under stress. Fig. 10 (b) (right) at 1000x depicts solid aggregates and visible cracks in the cement matrix, highlighting structural weaknesses and pointing out challenges in achieving uniform strength and durability.

Fig. 11 shows the microstructure of W2 samples with and without SP at 500x and 1000x magnifications. For the W2 sample with SP, Fig. 11 (a) (left) at 500x shows the cement matrix bonding with aggregates and WTBF, while cracks and voids present structural concerns despite reinforcement by WTBF. Fig. 11 (a) (right) at 1000x confirms the structural integrity provided by embedded WTBF in the cement matrix, yet visible cracks and voids suggest potential weaknesses persist. A previous study showed that SP incorporation could improve ITZs [41]. SP can improve the microstructure between fiber, matrix, and aggregate, leading to denser ITZs and higher strength, which is also in line with a previous study [42]. In contrast, for the W2 sample without SP, Fig. 11 (b) (left) at 500x reveals a cement matrix containing aggregates and WTBF, with visible cracks and voids indicating structural weaknesses. The loose ITZs around aggregates suggest areas of lower-strength structure. Fig. 11 (b) (right) at 1000x provides a closer view, highlighting these features more distinctly, including cracks running through the matrix and WTBF.

3.2.5. Shrinkage

Fig. 12 presents a comparison of shrinkage over time for four different sample groups. The samples include a reference group (Ref-S), W0.063–2, W2–8, and W8 + . Shrinkage is measured in micrometers per

Fig. 7. Calorimeter data of WTBF reinforced mortar with SP (a) Normalized heat flow; (b) Normalized total heat release.

Fig. 8. Comparison between WTBF reinforced mortar with and without SP (a) Normalized heat flow; (b) Normalized total heat release.

Fig. 9. Correlations between total heat release and compressive strength of mortars.

millimeter ($\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$) over a period of 28 days.

All samples exhibited a sharp shrinkage drop within the first 7 days, followed by a slower shrinkage rate in the later period. The reference mix (Ref-S) and the W2-8 and W8 + samples showed similar shrinkage trends, with final values around $-11,000 \mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$. The W0.063-2 mix, however, had a lower shrinkage magnitude, stabilizing at approximately $-8000 \mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$. The fine WTBF may have pozzolanic activity contributing to more gel formation and matrix expansion [6]. This leads to lower shrinkage than other samples. The rapid initial shrinkage suggests significant early moisture loss, which later slowed as the pore structure became less connected to the environment. Error bars indicate some variation, but the overall trends remain consistent.

3.3. Correlation between SP/fiber percentages and mortar properties

The results from the reference with superplasticizer (Ref-P) are selected as standard value (1) to normalize all the data with two decimals. Ref-P represents the optimized mix design with enhanced workability and strength due to the addition of SP in this study. All the raw data and its processing are in Table A1. The normalized ITZs numbers represent the loose (0) or dense (1) microstructure and the quantitative numbers are used to present the qualitative features of the microstructure.

3.3.1. Correlation between SP percentages and mortar properties

The correlation scatter plot highlights (shown in Fig. 13) the relationships between superplasticizer (SP) and various mortar properties. A strong positive correlation exists between SP and flowability (0.89), indicating that increasing SP enhances the flow of the mortar, as expected. This improved flowability is likely to contribute to better compaction and distribution of materials, thus enhancing other properties.

The interfacial transition zones (ITZs) exhibit a highly positive correlation with SP (1), indicating that the use of SP greatly improves the quality of ITZs, which are critical for the strength and durability of the composite. Better ITZs are associated with reduced porosity and enhanced adhesion between the binder, fiber, and aggregate, improving mortar performance. The flexural and compressive strengths also show significant positive correlations with SP (0.89 and 0.91, respectively), suggesting that adding SP strengthens the mortar. Simultaneously, the flowability shows positive correlations with compressive (0.97) and flexural strength (0.88) as well. This is likely due to the improved workability enabling better bonding and fewer voids in the matrix. The correlations between ITZs and compressive and flexural strength are also exhibited as 0.85 and 0.92. As mentioned, SP improves ITZs and denser microstructure, improving compressive and flexural strength. The significant contribution of SP to improving the ITZs is observed primarily in composites with a low water-to-cement (W/C) ratio [43]. A high W/C ratio can result in bleeding, segregation, and an increased water layer thickness around the aggregates, which diminishes the effectiveness of SP. In our study, WTBF-reinforced mortar without SP exhibited very poor workability, consistent with its classification as a low W/C ratio composite.

However, heat release during hydration presents a strong negative correlation with SP (-0.91), indicating that higher SP content slows down the hydration process. This reduction in heat release could be attributed to the dispersing effect of SP, which delays the contact between cement particles, reducing the rate of hydration. This is in line with a previous study that SP can retard the setting time and reduce the strength during the early ages [44].

3.3.2. Correlation between fiber percentage and mortar properties

The correlation scatter plot (shown in Fig. 14) illustrates how varying the fiber percentage affects the properties of the mortar. Noticeably, the fiber percentage shows a slight negative correlation with flowability (-0.45), suggesting that increasing the amount of fiber reduces the flowability of the mortar. This reduction in flowability could lead to challenges in workability, as fibers may impede the smooth flow of the mixture.

There is also a negative correlation between fiber percentage and

Fig. 10. Reference mortar (a) with / (b) without SP at 28 days.

Fig. 11. W2 mortar (a) with / (b) without SP at 28 days.

Fig. 12. Shrinkage for mortars up to 28 days.

both flexural and compressive strengths, with values of -0.25 and -0.29 , respectively. Although the negative impact is relatively mild, it suggests that a higher fiber content might not contribute as effectively to the mechanical strength of the mortar. This could be due to the low flowability and improper distribution of fibers, leading to weak zones or ineffective load transfer.

Heat release during hydration also shows a negative correlation (-0.38), indicating that the presence of fibers may slightly reduce the rate of heat release. This could be because fibers act as obstacles in the hydration process, slowing down the reaction between cement particles and water. The influence of WTBF on hydration heat release is limited due to the low absorption of WTBF, which differs from natural fiber. Zhao et al. [45] reported that incorporating bamboo fibers absorbs parts of the mixing water, reducing the amount available for cement hydration and thereby significantly slowing the reaction rate.

4. Discussion

The evaluation of SP on the mortar properties, as shown in the radar charts (Fig. 15), reveals several effects on different performance indicators. The samples with SP show notable improvements in various

aspects of mortar properties compared to their non-SP counterparts. Data from heat release was excluded since this was not about mortar performance.

The addition of SP significantly enhanced the flowability of all mortar mixes, as evidenced by normalized values showing improvements compared to non-SP samples, which is consistent with previous studies [46,47]. Besides, SP improved flexural strength across all fiber-reinforced samples, with the W1-P and W2-P mixes showing the highest increase. SP contributed to a better distribution of fibers in the matrix, resulting in this increase, which is in line with the previous study [48]. Regarding compressive strength, SP incorporation resulted in remarkable increases, especially in higher fiber content mixes (W1-P, W2-P). This improvement is attributed to better fiber dispersion as well. Moreover, SP improved ITZ quality, and the denser ITZs strengthened the bond between the paste, fibers, and matrix, further enhancing overall durability.

Fig. 16 provides an evaluation of the influence of different WTBF volume percentages on the mortar properties, both with and without SP. Increasing the WTBF content reduced the flowability of all mixes. However, the addition of SP significantly improved flowability across all fiber percentages, effectively mitigating the negative impact of higher fiber volumes. Higher WTBF percentages in non-SP matrices improved flexural strength, with W1 mixes showing the highest values. The addition of SP enhanced compressive and flexural strength in all fiber-reinforced mortars, also the W1-P mix achieving the highest flexural strength.

Based on their evaluated performance, Table 3 provides a perspective on the potential applications of WTBF-reinforced mixes. Across the various mix groups, the incorporation of WTBF and SP influenced flowability, compressive strength, and setting time, presenting different application potentials.

The W0.5 group demonstrates suitable compressive strength for rapid repair applications requiring quick setting [49]. On the other hand, the W1 and W2 groups, despite showing a slight reduction in flowability with acceptable strength, support their use in precast concrete. This aligns with industry requirements for moderate flowability and strength exceeding 40 MPa [50]. Notably, the SP-added variants (W0.5-P, W1-P, W2-P) exhibit significant improvements in flowability (up to 18 cm) and compressive strength (up to 65.1 MPa). These make them promising candidates for 3D printing usage. The flowability values for these mixes fall within the recommended range for 3D-printed concrete (13–18 cm), while their high compressive strength ensures

Fig. 13. Correlation scatter plot between SP and mortar properties.

Fig. 14. Correlation scatter plot between fiber% and mortar properties.

Fig. 15. Evaluation of SP on mortar properties.

A: Normalized flowability data
 B: Normalized flexural strength data
 C: Normalized compressive strength data

Fig. 16. Evaluation of fiber percentage on mortar properties.

Table 3
 Performance of WTBF-reinforced mixes: A perspective on applications.

Mix group	Parameter	Performance	Performance of the control group	Potential application	Information from Ref.
W0.5	Flow*	12.6 cm	13.38 cm	Rapid repairs, Precast concrete	Rapid repairs: Up to 170 mins initial setting time, high strength [49]. Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50].
	CS*	41.3 MPa	46.9 MPa		
	FS*	6.7 MPa	6.7 MPa		
	ST*	2.12 h	1.51 h		
W1	Flow	11.8 cm	13.38 cm	Precast concrete	Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50].
	CS	37.9 MPa	46.9 MPa		
	FS	6.9 MPa	6.7 MPa		
	ST	2.45 h	1.51 h		
W2	Flow	11 cm	13.38 cm	Precast concrete	Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50].
	CS	28.2 MPa	46.9 MPa		
	FS	5.9 MPa	6.7 MPa		
	ST	2.89 h	1.51 h		
W0.5-P	Flow	17.33 cm	18 cm	3D printing, SCC* (Flow data is very close), Precast concrete	3D printing: High compressive strength > 40 MPa. Flow between 13 and 18 cm. [39]. SCC: Flow is higher than 18 cm [51]. Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50]
	CS	65.1 MPa	65.2 MPa		
	FS	8 MPa	8.3 MPa		
	ST	2.51 h	2.14 h		
W1-P	Flow	15.93 cm	18 cm	3D printing, Precast concrete	3D printing: High compressive strength > 40 MPa. Flow between 13 and 18 cm [39]. Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50]
	CS	63.5 MPa	65.2 MPa		
	FS	9 MPa	8.3 MPa		
	ST	2.77 h	2.14 h		
W2-P	Flow	14.58 cm	18 cm	3D printing, Precast concrete	3D printing: High compressive strength > 40 MPa. Flow between 13 and 18 cm [39]. Precast concrete: Moderate flowability and compressive strength > 40 MPa [50]
	CS	56.6 MPa	65.2 MPa		
	FS	7.7 MPa	8.3 MPa		
	ST	3.01 h	2.14 h		

Flow* = Flowability; CS* = Compressive strength; FS* = Flexural strength; ST* = Initial setting time.
 The setting time data was from calorimeter data.
 SCC* = Self-compacting concrete.

structural reliability [39]. Only W0.5-P is close to the requirements for self-compacting concrete (SCC), which needs a flowability of up to 18 cm [51].

WTBF-reinforced mortars (with or without SP incorporation) show the feasibility across various construction scenarios. This study not only highlights their functional advantages but also demonstrates how waste-derived materials can contribute to sustainable construction solutions.

5. Conclusions

This study uses different volume percentages of wind turbine blade fiber (WTBF) as reinforcement in mortar to investigate the effect of SP on mechanical strength and the influence of fiber size on shrinkage. The results show that the SP leads to a homogeneous distribution of the WTBF in the cement paste leading to improved workability and strength. The different sizes of WTBF show different mechanisms for mitigating shrinkage. The following detailed conclusions can be drawn:

- The addition of SP enhances the workability of mortar, as reflected by the increased flow diameters with the increases ranging from 32.5 % to 37.5 %. A positive correlation was observed between SP addition and increased flowability (0.89). This enhancement directly correlates with better dispersion of materials due to SP addition, reducing internal friction between particles. Meanwhile, the SP-added WTBF-reinforced mortar is a promising candidate for 3D-printed fresh mixtures due to its suitable flowability, strength, and setting time.
- The addition of WTBF significantly decreases the compressive strength, and 1 vol% of WTBF shows the highest flexural strength (6.91 MPa without SP, 8.95 MPa with SP). SP enhances compressive strength, reducing the impact of WTBF incorporation. Furthermore, the positive correlation between increased flowability and strength (0.97 for compressive strength, 0.88 for flexural strength) suggests that improved workability leads to better compaction, resulting in stronger mortar strength.
- The incorporation of SP delays hydration peaks by about 8 hours and reduces heat flow. This delay is due to SP slowing the initial cement-water interaction, prolonging setting times and lowering heat release. The inverse correlation between SP content and heat release ($r = -0.91$) highlights the trade-off between improved workability and slower hydration kinetics, optimizing curing conditions for better mechanical properties.
- The use of SP improved the microstructural characteristics, particularly in the Interfacial Transition Zones (ITZs) between the WTBF and cement matrix. The correlation analysis showed that SP strongly enhanced ITZs, which were positively correlated with compressive strength ($r = 0.91$) and flexural strength ($r = 0.85$). This densifica-

tion reduced porosity and improved fiber-matrix bonding, leading to stronger composites.

- Different WTBF sizes affected shrinkage differently. Fine fibers (0.063–2 mm) showed pozzolanic reactivity, reducing shrinkage by expanding the matrix. Larger fibers (>8 mm) acted as physical fillers with less chemical interaction, retaining shrinkage. This highlights the potential to optimize fiber size for shrinkage control in specific applications.

SP and fiber content show a synergistic effect on mortar properties. WTBF incorporation improves flexural strength but reduces flowability and compressive strength, presenting a challenge in practical applications. SP effectively addresses this by significantly enhancing workability without compromising the mechanical performance provided by the fibers. The combination of SP and WTBF leads to an optimized balance between fresh and hardened properties, making it a promising solution for sustainable construction materials in different application scenarios.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Reascos Huber: Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Liu Tao:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Kirkelund Gunvor Marie:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Mughal Umair Abid:** Investigation. **Lima Ana Teresa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Table A1
Normalized data from the mortar samples

	Ref	W0.5	W1	W2	Ref-P	W0.5-P	W1-P	W2-P
Flowability	13.38	12.6	11.8	11	18	17.33	15.93	14.58
Normalized flowability data	0.74	0.70	0.66	0.61	1	0.96	0.89	0.81
Flexural strength	6.68	6.74	6.91	5.93	8.31	8.03	8.95	7.65
Normalized flexural strength data	0.80	0.81	0.83	0.71	1	0.97	1.08	0.92
Compressive strength	46.89	41.29	37.86	28.15	65.23	65.14	63.5	56.58
Normalized compressive strength data	0.72	0.63	0.58	0.43	1	1.00	0.97	0.87
Hydration heat	260	258	264	253	242	232	222	221
Normalized heat release data	1.07	1.07	1.09	1.05	1	0.96	0.92	0.91
ITZs	0	-	-	0	1	-	-	1
Normalized ITZs data	0	-	-	0	1	-	-	1

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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